

National Aeronautics and
Space Administration

Software for the Science Mission Directorate

Welcome

Kevin Murphy

Chief Science Data Officer

Office of the Chief Science Data Officer

CSDO: Kevin Murphy

GOAL 1

Develop and Implement Capabilities to Enable Open Science

GOAL 2

Continuous Evolution of Data and Computing Systems

GOAL 3

Harness the Community and Strategic Partnerships for Innovation

OCSDO Enables Open Science

Each activity helps OCSDO achieve its goals of enabling Open Science for NASA.

DATA & COMPUTING SERVICES

Core Services for Science Discovery

Developing core data and computing services to enable open science

DATA SCIENCE/AI

Data Science and Artificial Intelligence

Implementing innovative data science tools, with a focus on inclusion and expanding the accessibility of scientific information

OPEN SCIENCE

Open Science implementation

This includes Policy development, education, incentives, and advocacy on open science and software

Introduction

Steve Crawford

Senior Program Executive for Data
and Computing

NASA's Software Legacy

```

SAPT ASSEMBLE REVISION 001 OF AGC PROGRAM LMY99 BY NASA 2021172-061 16:27 JULY 14, 1969 LNYAI
L ATTITUDE MANEUVER ROUTINE USER'S PAGE NO.
R0193 ( 6 7 8)
R0194
R0196 INDEX REGISTER X1 MUST BE LOADED WITH THE COMPLEMENT OF THE STARTING ADDRESS FOR M1, AND
R0198
R0199 LOADED WITH THE COMPLEMENT OF THE STARTING ADDRESS FOR M2. THE ROUTINE USES THE FIRST 20 LOC
R0201 DOWN LIST. THE FIRST ELEMENT OF THE MATRIX APPEARS IN PDD. PUSH UP FOR M.
R0203
R0205
R0206 TRANSPOS
R0207
R0208 THIS ROUTINE TRANSPOSES A 3X3 MATRIX AND LEAVES THE RESULT IN THE PUSH DOWN LIST, I.E.,
R0210 * * T
R0211 M = M1
R0212
R0213 INDEX REGISTER X1 MUST CONTAIN THE COMPLEMENT OF THE STARTING ADDRESS FOR M1. PUSH UP FOR THE
R0215 SEQUENT COMPONENTS OF M. THIS SUBROUTINE ALSO USES THE FIRST 20 LOCATIONS OF THE PUSH DOWN LIST.
R0216
R0218 CDU TO DCM
R0219
R0220
R0221 THIS SUBROUTINE CONVERTS THREE CDU ANGLES IN T(MPAC) TO A DIRECTION COSINE MATRIX (SCALED BY 2) RELATING
R0223 THE CORRESPONDING S/C ORIENTATIONS TO THE STABLE MEMBER FRAME. THE FORMULAS FOR THIS CONVERSION ARE
R0225
R0226 M = COSY COSZ
R0227 0
R0228 M = -COSY SINZ COSX + SINY SINX
R0229 1
R0230 M = COSY SINZ SINX + SINY COSX
R0231 2
R0232 M = SINZ
R0233 3
R0234 M = COSZ COSX
R0235 4
R0236 M = -COSZ SINX
R0237 5
R0238 M = -SINY COSZ
R0239 6
R0240 M = SINY SINZ COSX + COSY SINX
R0241 7

```


Mary W. Jackson worked at the Langley Research Center.

Margaret Hamilton with the Apollo software she and her team at MIT produced.

JWST Calibration Software

Developed openly on GitHub allowing the community access prior to launch.

Builds and contributes to the scientific Python environment.

spacetelescope/jwst Public

Code Issues (549) Pull requests (31) Discussions Actions Projects Wiki Security Insights

master 74 branches 146 tags

Go to file Add file Code About

nbushouse Clean up change log and README for B9.1 and 9.1.1 releases (#7448) 22acc46 8 hours ago 7,418 commits

- .github changes for [axxx] release (#7384) 5 days ago
- docs JP-2013 NIRSpec leakal and nodded exposures (#7426) 2 weeks ago
- jwst JP-3079 Ensure all imprint exposures are include in associations (#7... 4 days ago
- pytest_crds Add --report-crds-context pytest option (#6070) last year
- codecov.yml Use Codecov carryforward flags (#5406) 2 years ago
- .gitignore move scripts into subpackage so that they can be packaged with 'en... last month
- .readthedocs.yml use canonical filename for RTD configuration (#7050) 4 months ago
- CHANGES.rst Clean up change log and README for B9.1 and 9.1.1 releases (#7448) 8 hours ago

Python library for science observations from the James Webb Space Telescope

[jwst-pipeline.readthedocs.io/en/latest/](#)

[python](#) [astronomy](#) [jwst](#)

Readme View license Code of conduct Cite this repository 392 stars 30 watching 132 forks

<https://github.com/spacetelescope/jwst>

Software in NASA Science

Due to the nature of Earth and Space Science, software is integral to every step of the scientific process: from information gathering from space based detectors to sharing results.

Open Source Software Policy Options for NASA Earth and Space Science

2018 [Report](#) that provided recommendations for open source software and research software for Earth and Space Science..

This included how to transition the community, funding for support, and policy options.

Previous recommendations from 2011 NASA Open Source Summit.

We've made progress...

- **ROSES** Open Source Tools, Frameworks, and Libraries and Supplement for Open Source Science support
- **Updated policies** for the Science Information Policy for the Science Mission Directorate and NPR 2210.1E **Release of NASA Software**
- Improvements to the **software release process**
- **Recognition and incentives** for scientific software

... and there is more work to be done

- **Update process and policies** related to scientific and mission software
- **Increase** sharing and **collaboration** across NASA
- **Adopting new technology** and practices into software development
- **Improve inclusive practices** and diversity of career opportunities

Software for the Science Mission Directorate

The workshop aims to explore the current opportunities and challenges for the various categories and lifecycle stages of software that are relevant for activities funded by the NASA Science Mission Directorate (SMD).

The workshop will be virtual with an in-person option at NASA Headquarters in Washington, DC from May 7-9.

Website:

<https://science.data.nasa.gov/news/software-workshop-2024/>

Objectives

- Bring together those interested in software for the NASA Science Mission Directorate to **facilitate new collaborations** across centers and sciences.
- **Identify opportunities and challenges** in different stages of the software lifecycle.
- **Identify software being developed**, areas of expertise, resources, and best practices for the NASA software community.
- **Provide community feedback** to prioritize paths forward.

Outcomes:

- Presentations and recordings of talks will be shared.
- Produce a brief report summarizing the main takeaways from the meeting.

People

Executive Committee

Lead: Rebecca Ringuette, *NASA GSFC*

Sponsor: Steven Crawford, *NASA Office of the Chief Science Data Officer*

Brian Thomas, *NASA GSFC*

Mark Parsons, *University of Alabama, Huntsville/NASA OCSDO*

Demitri Muna, *Agile Sciences/NASA OCSDO*

Holly Norton, *Booz-Allen Hamilton/NASA OCSDO*

Paul Fertitta, *Booz-Allen Hamilton/NASA*

Program Committee

Chair: Rebecca Ringuette, *NASA GSFC*

Crystal Gummo, *NASA LaRC*

Jon Jenkins, *NASA ARC*

Maria Kuznetsova, *NASA GSFC*

Paul Ramirez, *Jet Propulsion Laboratory*

Amanda Saravia-Butler, *NASA ARC*

Leo Singer, *NASA GSFC*

Josh Steele, *Applied Physics Laboratory*

Ashish Acharya, *University of Alabama, Huntsville/NASA MSFC*

HQ OCSDO: Kevin Murphy, Andy Mitchell, Elena Steponaitis, Rachel Paseka, JL Galache Amy Truong

HQ: Roopesh Ojha, Alessandra Aloisi, Robin Fergason, Katie Baynes, Joel Scott, Katherine Saad

Code of Conduct

By participating in this workshop, I will:

- Conduct myself with integrity, respect, honesty, and credibility.
- Approach all events, activities, and discussions with the highest ethical standards of professionalism and personal conduct.
- Avoid personal attacks or other activities that cause damage to other participants or the hosts.
- Value and respect diversity of views and opinions.

Reporting Unacceptable Behavior:

- If you are the subject of unacceptable behavior or have witnessed any such behavior, please immediately notify a meeting host.
- Notification should be done by contacting a host via direct chat or emailing your concern [to steven.m.crawford@nasa.gov](mailto:steven.m.crawford@nasa.gov)
- Anyone experiencing or witnessing behavior that constitutes an immediate or serious threat to public safety is advised to contact 911 or your local emergency number.

Code of Conduct: <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1n2mFphAyC3ddHqz0Ov3RSews6PQeQRLcMZMCRnN30dg/edit>

Learn, Participate, and Have Fun

We get to talk about software for three days!

Meet colleagues and future collaborators:

- What code are you most proud of?
- What is your funniest software story?

Be present and online -set your out of office and join in the chat

Learn about what others are doing! Think about where you might participate.

Be agile - self organize into the areas that

Logistics

Rebecca Ringuette

Principal Open Science Scientist

Heliophysics Digital Resource Library

Steve Crawford

Science Data Officer

Important Rooms

- Emergency exits
- Bathrooms
- Elevators
- Breakout rooms

Workshop Agenda

<https://go.nasa.gov/3Up4zWY>

- Website link
- Workshop Google drive link
- Padlet link
- IO Tool link
- The WebEx link and password **are in your email.**

This password will also be needed to access the Miro boards.

2024 NASA Software Workshop Agenda

Website: <https://science.data.nasa.gov/news/software-workshop-2024/>

[Overall Google Folder](#)

[Discussion Topic Padlet](#)

IO Tool

Please see your email for the WebEx link and passcode.

Tuesday, May 7, 2024

Time (ET)	Agenda Item	Presenter/Notes/Links
Day 1, Session 1: Software at NASA - Opportunities and Challenges		Day 1 Google Folder Moderator: Mark Parsons
8:30am	Check in and registration	
9:30 am - 9:50 am	Welcome and Purpose	Kevin Murphy and Steve Crawford
9:50 am - 10:05 am	Organization, Logistics, and Questions Submissions	Rebecca Ringuette
10:05 am - 10:25 am	Invited Talk 1	Tasha Snow
10:25 am - 10:45 am	Invited Talk 2	Bill Wohler
10:45 am - 11:05 am	Invited Talk 3	Dan Crichton
11:05 am - 11:10 am	Discussion Topics Submissions	Rebecca Ringuette

Workshop guidebook

Find many important details on how to access and use the technology in the workshop guidebook, which is linked from the workshop website.

2024 NASA Software Workshop Attendee Resource Guidebook

Before You Go - NCTS Approval (NASA Official In-Person Attendees Only) 2

Platform Information 3

Google Drive 3

Webex 3

Webex Layout for Plenary sessions 4

Breakout Rooms in Webex 5

IO Tool 6

Padlet 7

Submitting a discussion topic 7

Voting on a discussion topic 10

Miro 12

Getting to the right Miro board 12

Interacting with the Miro board 14

Meeting Location 16

Getting to NASA HQ 17

Metro Information 17

Parking at NASA Headquarters 17

Connecting to the wifi 18

Nearby Food and Drink Options 18

Near Site Lodging and Accommodations 19

Things to do in Washington, DC 19

Types of Contributions Needed

- We will have discussion sessions for the second half of the workshop. Please contribute discussion topics for these on padlet.
- When it is voting time, please rate the discussion topics on padlet.
- Please help us take notes in the Google docs for each session.
- Ask questions in plenary sessions using the IO tool.
- Ask questions in breakout sessions using the WebEx Q&A.
- Contribute thoughts to the Miro boards during discussion sessions.

With great conversations comes great... food!

Continue your great conversations at one of the many local restaurants and coffee shops!

Also note potentially interesting local events linked from the guidebook *starting tonight!*

Nearby Food and Drink Options

There are a variety of dining options available to you when visiting Headquarters.

- 2 Sisters: 400 C St SW, Washington, DC 20024. Phone: 202-554-0099
- 21 Amendment Bar & Grill: 550 C St SW, Washington, DC 20024. Phone: 202-554-1780
- Atrium Cafe: Located in Jinnie Mae Business Center, 400 Virginia Ave SW, Washington, DC 20024. Phone: 202-863-7590
- Capital Bistro: 550 C St SW, Washington, DC 20024. Phone: 202-479-4000
- Casey's Coffee: 355 E. St SW, Washington, DC 20024. Phone: 202-488-8800
- CitizenM: 550 School St. SW, Washington, DC 20024. Phone: 202-747-2145
- Hyatt Rooftop Bar: 400 E St. SW, Washington, DC 20024. Phone: 202-803-6110
- Jaliyaa Coffee: NASA HQ Exchange. <https://nasa.sharepoint.com/sites/hq-exchange> (scroll down for hours and menu)
- McDonald's: 400 C Street, SW. 202-484-0803. Offers a complimentary WiFi hotspot. Phone: 202-484-0803
- Potbelly Sandwich Shop: 409 3rd Street SW, next to the Federal Center SW Metro Station. Phone: 202-863-3965. Fax: 202-863-3956. Online and phone/fax orders are welcome.
- [View More Places](#)

What if...?

- **Code of conduct** issues or questions:
Steve Crawford, steven.m.crawford@nasa.gov
- **In-Person** issues or questions:
Paul Fertitta, paul.d.fertitta@nasa.gov
- **Virtual technology** issues or questions:
Holly Norton, holly.e.norton@nasa.gov
- **All other issues** or questions:
Rebecca Ringuette, rebecca.ringuette@nasa.gov